

Clinical Exposome of Patient-Reported Outcomes for Patients with Metastatic Breast Cancer (CePROs)

Comprehensive Centre for Oncology - ICO

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INTRODUCTION

The exposome refers to all exposures to which an individual is subjected through out lifetime. The most immediate sphere for patients with severe conditions such as metastatic breast cancer is likely to be the clinical than the environmental exposome. Recently, clinical research data and Electronic Health Records (EHRs) have become a potential source for tracing the clinical exposome. Since Patient-Reported Outcomes (PROs) are sensitive to the exposome, this conceptual study examines the methodological implication of conducting clinical exposome research on PROs.

Window of susceptibility (WoS)

Non-communicable diseases (NCDs)

The scopes of exposome

1. Time perspective
 - a. Lifetime exposome
 - b. Exposome during WoS
 - c. Exposome of parents
 - d. After disease onset
 - ...
2. Disease
 - a. Diabetes
 - b. Autisme
 - c. Cancers
 - ...
3. Environment
 - a. Chemical exposome
 - b. Social exposome
 - ...

Characteristics of exposome studies

1. Mixture of exposures
2. High dimensional data
3. Real-world data
4. Hypothesis-generating
5. Temporal considerations
6. Outcome specific

METHODS

We performed a scoping review along with an analysis of real-world clinical data. We adapted exposome methods to clinical information by focusing on hypothesis-driven processes within high-dimensional data and on generating new insights into how specific clinical exposures are mapped to specific PRO dimensions.

RESULTS

Unstructured information in electronic Clinical Research Forms (eCRFs) and EHRs including heterogeneous entries (e.g. misspellings, synonyms, commercial and generic names, deviations in expressions) will be refined into specific structured variables (e.g. co-medications, family history or occasional symptoms) using large language models (LLMs). Structured data in eCRFs, such as disease characteristics, treatments, comorbidities, critical clinical events, psychometric measures, and medical procedures in EHRs, will be used directly and in combination to describe the clinical patterns of the disease and treatment pathway. A minimum of 200 longitudinal clinical variables times the number of repeated measures will be used. The exposome-wide association study (ExWAS) will then screen each clinical exposure with individual PRO questions and dimensions. We will use cross-validated Lasso regression models to assess how a set of clinical variables affect PROs.

A **framework** making the most of routinely collected big data such as Patient Reported Outcomes Measurement Information System (PROMIS)

A fundamental step enabling the mapping between clinical exposome and PRO dimensions

Isolating the effect of clinical exposome components allows PROs to be used for multiple **clinical implications**

Most people do not have PROs (e.g., QLQ-C30) measured before cancer onset

Baseline (BL) PROs are a result of pre-evaluation health conditions

BC - Breast cancer
PD - Primary diagnosis
Relap. - relapse
Ann. - Diagnosis announcement

Implications for **Health Economics and Outcomes Research (HEOR)**

1. Real-World data use (e.g. Cost-effectiveness studies)
2. Expanded Definition of Healthcare Value (e.g. Value Based Health Care, VBHC)
3. Patient-centered research (e.g. Optimizing Treatment De-Escalation)

RESULTS

EPICURE Cohort

ICO Comprehensive Cancer Centre, Saint-Herblain (Nantes), France

- ➔ Metastatic breast cancer
- ➔ High-dimensional and heterogeneous data
- ➔ Multiple scientific objectives including
 - a. mechanism of treatment resistance
 - b. cancer management
 - c. PROs research
 - d. omics sciences
 - e. internal and external exposome
- ➔ First dataset for analyzing more than 6000 variables retrieved from 46 sub-datasets

Structured variables based on needs analysis

Large Language Models

Heterogeneous entries in EHRs

misspellings, synonyms, commercial and generic names, deviations in expressions

Disease pathway

Comorbidities

- (Examples of free text entries in French)
- DIABETE
 - DIABETE DE TYPE I
 - DIABETE DE TYPE II
 - DIARRHÉE CHRONIQUE
 - DISCOPATHIE
 - DYSLIPIDÉMIE
 - Diabète de type II
 - Dylipidémie
 - Dépression
 - EMBOLIE PULMONAIRE
 - ENDOPROTHÈSE ARTERIELLE
 - EXTRACTION DENTAIRE
 - Embolie pulmonaire
 - Extraction dentaire
 - FAUSSE COUCHE
 - FIBROMYALGIE
 - Fracture
 - GYNÉCOLOGIE
 - GYNÉCOLOGIQUE
 - HERNIE OMBILICALE
 - HTA
 - HYPERCHOLESTÉROLEMIE
 - HYPERTHYROÏDIE
 - HYPOTHYROÏDIE
 - HYSTERECTOMIE
 - HYSTÉROSCOPIE
 - HYSTÉROSCOPIE
 - HYSTÉROUSALPINGOGRAPHE
 - Hypothyroïdie
 - Hypothyroïdie
 - Hystérectomie
 - IVG

Comedications

- (Examples of free text entries in French)
- TIACOLCHICOSIDE
 - TICAGRELOR
 - TINZAPARINE
 - TINZAPARINE SODIQUE
 - TINZAPARINE SODIQUE ANTI XA/O,7ML
 - TINZAPARINE SODIQUE 10000
 - TINZAPARINE SODIQUE 14000IU ANTI XA/O...
 - TINZAPARINE SODIQUE 18000 IU ANTI XA/O...
 - TIORFAN
 - TITANOREINE
 - TIXOCORTOL PIVALATE
 - TIZAPARINE SODIUM
 - TOPALGIC
 - TRAMADOL
 - TRAMADOL 100M/2ML
 - TRAMADOL 50MG
 - TRAMADOL CHLORHYDRATE
 - TRAMADOL CHLORHYDRATE
 - TRAMADOL LP
 - TRAMADOL PARACETAMOL
 - TRAMADOL PARACETAMOL 37,5/325MG
 - TRAMADOL PARACETAMOL 37,5MG/325MG
 - TRAMADOL/PARACETAMOL 37,5MG/325MG ARROW
 - TRAMODOL PARACETAMOL
 - TRAVOPROST
 - TRÉLEÇON ELIPTA
 - TRIMEBUTINE
 - TRIMEBUTINE 100MG
 - TRIMETHYLPHTHOLOROGLUCINOL
 - TRIMETHYLPHTHOLOROGLUCINOL
 - TRIMETHYLPHTHOLOROGLUCINOL

Chemotherapy

- (Examples of free text entries in French)
- 3 EC 12TAXOL
 - 3 FEC + 3 TAXOTERE
 - 3 FEC 100
 - 3 FEC 100 DOCETAXEL
 - 3 FEC 100 + 3 TAXOTERE
 - 3 FEC 3 DOCETAXEL
 - 3 TAXOTERE
 - 3EC
 - 3FEC 100
 - 6 TAXOL AVASTIN
 - 6 TAXOTERE
 - TRASTUZUMAB
 - PERTUZUMAB
 - 8 TAXOL
 - HEBDOMADAIRE
 - ABBVIE M12 914 (TAXOL+CARBO)
 - AC
 - AC PACLITAXEL
 - ADRIAMYCINE
 - ADRIAMYCINE
 - CYCLOPHOSPHAMIDE
 - ADRIAMYCINE
 - CYCLOPHOSPHAMIDE
 - BEVACIZUMAB
 - PACLITAXEL
 - CAELYX
 - CAPECITABINE
 - CARBO
 - CARBOPLATINE

Family Hist. of cancer

- (Examples of free text entries in French)
- Aucun ATCD
 - BRONCHIQUE
 - CANCER EN LIEN AVEC TABAC
 - CANCER LIE A L'AMIANTE
 - CANCER NON PRECISE
 - CAVITE BUCCALE
 - PHARYNX, PARTIES AUTR.
 - CEREBRAL
 - COL UTERIN
 - COLON
 - COLON GRAND PERE
 - MATERNEL
 - COLON ONCLE
 - PATERNEL
 - ENCEPHALE
 - ESTOMAC
 - FOIE
 - FOIE ET VOIES BILAIRES
 - INTRAHEPATIQUES
 - FRERE : MELANOME 2008
 - FRERE OESOPHAGE
 - INTENTIN GRELE
 - K
 - LANGUE
 - LEUCEMIE

RESULTS

Mapping from Clinical Exposome to PRO dimensions

Clinical exposome components :	possible effects on:	PRO dimensions :
Diagnosis announcement	EF (...)	AP - Appetite loss
Conservative Surgery	EF, PA, FA, CF (...)	BI - Body Image
Mastectomy	BI, BS, SF (...)	BS - Breast Symptoms
Chemotherapy protocol A	FA, PF, NV (...)	CF - Cognitive Functioning
Chemotherapy protocol B	FA, PF, AP (...)	CO - Constipation
Imaging progression report	EM, SF (...)	DI - Diarrhoea
Imaging remission report	EM, FU (...)	EF - Emotional Functioning
Hormonotherapy	ST (...)	FA - Fatigue
Phytotherapy	CO, FA (...)	FU - Future perspective
Diabetes	AP, CO, DI, PF (...)	HL - Hair Loss
Tendinopathy	PF, PA (...)	NV - Nausea and Vomiting
Rheumatoid arthritis	PF, PA, SF (...)	PA - Pain
Parkinson's disease	PF, SF, CF (...)	PF - Physical Functioning
Chronic respiratory disease	PF, SF, CF (...)	SF - Social Functioning
Family history of cancer	EM, FU (...)	ST - Systemic side effects
35 years of breast cancer survival since PD	EF, SF, FU (...)	(...)
Triple negative breast cancer	EM, FU (...)	(...)

Temporal considerations

Statistical methods for clinical exposome variables selection and analysis

ExWAS - Exposome-wide association study

ENET - Elastic-Net

DLNM - Distributed Lag Non-linear Models

sPLS - Sparse Partial Least-Squares Regression

DSA - Deletion-Substitution-Addition Algorithm

NPLS - Sparse N-Way Partial Least-Square

BKM - Bayesian Kernel Machine

Jugement criteria:

Sensitivity

False discorery rate

(...)

CONCLUSION

The clinical exposome framework is a critical component for both the patient-centered care and research on PROs. It helps map patient clinical exposures to PROs dimension and isolate their effects to specific dimensions. This serves the value-based care ultimately.

CONTACT INFORMATION

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